

Equilibrium Study on the Complex Formation of Copper(II), Cobalt(II) and Nickel(II) with 2-Chloroacetylaminomethyl Benzimidazole

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Combined pH-metric and spectrophotometric study on the complex formation of M^{2+} ions with 2-chloroacetylaminomethyl benzimidazole (L) has indicated the formation of a variety of complexes: ML^{2+} , ML_2^{2+} , $M(H_{-1}L)^+$, $M(H_{-1}L)(L)^+$, $M(H_{-1}L)_2$ and $M(H_{-1}L)(OH)$ where, $M = Cu, Co$ and Ni . Formation constants of the complexes were determined at $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$ in 50% (v/v) dioxan-water medium having a fixed ionic strength of $\mu = 0.2 M$ ($NaNO_3$) and correlated with the modes of bonding of the ligand in these complexes.

STUDY of imidazole and benzimidazole complexes of transition metal ions is of considerable interest, as these ligands are closely related to biological systems involving the histidine moiety and vitamin B_{12} coenzyme. 2-Chloroacetylaminomethyl benzimidazole (CAB) contains three potential metal binding sites, viz. the N_3 -benzimidazole, the amide ($-CONH-$) moiety and the side-chain Cl atom (1,2). Combined pH-metric and spectrophotometric study on the reaction of CAB (hereafter, L) with Cu^{2+} , Co^{2+} and Ni^{2+} has been intended to see the modes of coordination by the amide moiety having a benzimidazole group and a side-chain Cl in suitable positions to provide coordination.

Experimental

The ligand CAB was prepared by condensing 2-aminomethylbenzimidazole¹ with chloroacetyl chloride in dry benzene medium and removing the hydrogen chloride by distillation under reduced pressure. The ligand CAB came out as shiny white niddle shaped crystals. These were collected by filtration, washed several times with hot benzene and finally recrystallised from ethanol and air-dried, m.p. 172° (Found: C, 53.72; H, 4.40; N, 18.84; Cl, 15.92. $C_{10}H_{10}N_3OCl$ calcd. for: C, 53.69; H, 4.47; N, 18.79; Cl, 15.88%); λ_{max} (EtOH) ($\log \epsilon$) 275 (3.88) and 245 nm (3.85); ν_{max} (KBr)² 3 140, (NH), 1 660 (amide I), 1 530 (amide II) and 1 300 cm^{-1} (amide III).

The procedure for pH-metric titrations was the same as described earlier³. Some representative pH-titrations curves are shown in Fig. 1. Formation constants of the complexes were calculated through computer programme SCOGS⁴ with the aid of a WIPRO PC XT computer system. Preliminary estimates of some of the constants supplied to the computer as input data were evaluated by analysing the pH-titration curves according to the procedure of Irving and Rossotti⁵. The computer refined values

Fig. 1. pH Titration curves of CAB in the absence and in presence of metal (Cu^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+}) nitrate at $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$ in 50% (v/v) dioxan-water medium at ionic strength $\mu = 0.2 M$ $NaNO_3$: (1) $0.01 M$ HNO_3 ; (2) $0.01 M$ $HNO_3 + 0.01 M$ ligand CAB (LH^+); (3) $0.01 M$ $HNO_3 + 0.001 M$ Cu^{2+} ; (4) $0.01 M$ $HNO_3 + 0.001 M$ Co^{2+} ; (5) $0.01 M$ $HNO_3 + 0.001 M$ Ni^{2+} ; (6) $0.01 M$ $HNO_3 + 0.01 M$ CAB (LH^+) + $0.002 M$ Cu^{2+} ; (7) $0.01 M$ $HNO_3 + 0.01 M$ CAB (LH^+) + $0.002 M$ Co^{2+} ; (8) $0.01 M$ $HNO_3 + 0.01 M$ CAB (LH^+) + $0.002 M$ Ni^{2+} .

TABLE 1—PROTON-LIGAND AND METAL-LIGAND CONSTANTS WITH CAB
Temp. = 30 ± 0.1° ; Medium : 50% (v/v) Dioxan-Water, Ionic strength μ = 0.2(M) NaNO₃.

	Cu		Co	Ni
log K _{CuL} ^{Cu}	3.51 ± 0.02			
log K _{CuL₂} ^{Cu}	6.11 ± 0.03			
log K _{Cu(L)₂} ^H	-0.07 ± 0.02	pK _{M+L} ^H	4.60 ± 0.05	5.54 ± 0.05
log K _{Cu(H₋₁L)(L)} ^H	-6.85 ± 0.05	pK _{M(H₋₁L)+L} ^H	11.00 ± 0.05	12.30 ± 0.05
log K _{Cu(L)} ^H	-1.42 ± 0.03			
pK _{Cu(H₋₁L)} ^H	7.96 ± 0.06	pK _{M(H₋₁L)} ^H	7.70 ± 0.05	7.89 ± 0.05
pK _{Cu} ^H	6.82 ± 0.05	pK _M ^H	8.22 ± 0.04	8.52 ± 0.04
pK _{Cu} ^{2H}	13.60 ± 0.05	pK _M ^{2H}	17.10 ± 0.06	17.48 ± 0.06

of the constants (Table 1) were used to calculate the species distribution curves (Figs. 2-4).

Results and Discussion

Proton-ligand equilibria: In the absence of metal ions the ligand CAB in the form of LH⁺ showed a single buffer region (Fig. 1) in the pH range 3-6 due to deprotonation of the N₃⁺H benzimidazolium moiety^{6,7} according to

Absence of any other buffer region at higher pH values ruled out the possibility of deprotonation of amide bond (CONH) in the absence of metal ion. pK_{LH}^H value was found to be 4.53 ± 0.02.

Cu²⁺-CAB equilibria: Cu²⁺-CAB mixtures gave two buffer regions at pH 2-5 and 6-8 each consuming two moles of base per Cu²⁺. A blue turbidity appeared at pH ≈ 8 which passed into solution (pH > 10) on addition of two additional moles of base. As the buffer region corresponding to the Cu²⁺-CAB complexation equilibria was quite close to the hydrolytic equilibria of Cu²⁺(aq.)

ion, the formation of hydroxo complexes were also taken into consideration in calculating the metal-ligand constants. The following species: LH⁺, L, Cu²⁺, Cu(OH)⁺, Cu(OH)₂, CuL²⁺, CuL₂²⁺, Cu(H₋₁L)⁺, Cu(H₋₁L)L⁺, Cu(H₋₁L)₂ and Cu(H₋₁L)(OH) were considered to be present in the complexation equilibria. Cu²⁺-CAB²⁻ complex distribution curves (Fig 2) showed that at pH 2-5 the ligand CAB was in the LH⁺ form and therefore, the complexes CuL²⁺

Fig 2 Species distribution curves of Cu²⁺-CAB system: (1) LH⁺, F_L, L, (2) Cu(OH)⁺, (3) Cu(OH)₂, (4) CuL²⁺, F_M, Cu²⁺, (5) CuL₂²⁺, (6) Cu(H₋₁L)⁺, (7) Cu(H₋₁L)(L)⁺, (8) Cu(H₋₁L)₂, (9) Cu(H₋₁L)(OH).

and CuL₂²⁺ must have resulted according to the equilibria,

It is evident from these complex distribution curves that the $\text{Cu}(\text{H}_{-1}\text{L})^+$, $\text{Cu}(\text{L})(\text{H}_{-1}\text{L})^+$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{H}_{-1}\text{L})_2$ complexes resulted from deprotonation of the $\text{Cu}(\text{L})^{2+}$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{L})_2^{2+}$ complexes according to equilibria (4-6),

involving substitution of the amide proton of the ligand by Cu^{2+} ions. The ligand, $(\text{H}_{-1}\text{L})^-$ in these complexes resulted from amide deprotonation form of L leading to the coordination of amide nitrogen atom to Cu^{2+} ion. The possibility of deprotonation of the complex $\text{Cu}(\text{H}_{-1}\text{L})^+$ according to

could not be ruled out as it was quite likely to take up molecules of solvent water to provide a square-planar geometry⁸ to Cu^{2+} . The complexes $\text{Cu}(\text{H}_{-1}\text{L})_2$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{H}_{-1}\text{L})(\text{OH})$ being electroneutral, possibly precipitated at the later stages of the titration.

Comparable magnitudes of $\log K_{\text{CuL}}^{\text{Cu}}$ and $\log K_{\text{Cu}(\text{L})_2}^{\text{Cu}}$ with those of benzimidazole and imidazole ligands^{6,7} indicated monodentate coordination of Cu^{2+} in CuL and CuL_2 complexes (3 and 4) by the N_3 -benzimidazole atom of the ligand CAB,

(3)

(4)

(5)

The $\log K_{\text{CuL}}^{\text{Cu}}$ values for typical N-N bidentate ligands, viz. 2,2'-bipyridin⁹, 1,10-phenanthroline¹⁰, ethylenediamine¹¹ are 6 to 8 log units higher. Electronic spectra of 1 : 5 Cu^{2+} -CAB mixtures at different pH values were not comparable to those of the 1 : 5 Cu^{2+} -chloroacetate mixtures under identical conditions. This ruled out the possibility of (O, Cl) bidentate coordination (5) of Cu^{2+} via the amide carbonyl oxygen atom and the terminal Cl atom of the ligand.

The 1 : 5 Cu^{2+} -CAB mixture showed λ_{max} at 650 nm at pH 10.2. The calculated¹² λ_{max} values¹² for a square-planar $[\text{Cu}(\text{N-amide})_2(\text{N-imidazole})_2]$ geometry should be around 538 nm. This 112 nm red-shift of λ_{max} was probably the outcome of apical coordination of Cu^{2+} by the solvent molecules or by the terminal Cl atoms of the coordinated ligand ions, $(\text{H}_{-1}\text{L}^-)$ giving rise to a distorted octahedral geometry (6) to the $\text{Cu}(\text{H}_{-1}\text{L})_2$ complex.

(6)

M^{2+} -CAB equilibria ($\text{M}^{2+} = \text{Ni}^{2+}, \text{Co}^{2+}$): Buffer regions corresponding to the complexation equilibria of Co^{2+} and Ni^{2+} were observed at pH 7.0-8.5 (Fig. 1), where the free ligand was exclusively in the L form. Two moles of base per mole of metal ions were consumed in this pH range with appearance of turbidity, which passed into solution after addition of two further moles of base (pH $\approx$ 11). As the metal-ligand equilibria were overlapping with the hydrolytic equilibria of M^{2+} (aq.) ions, the formation of hydroxo complex was also taken into consideration in the calculation of metal-ligand constants.

Spectrophotometric study of the M^{2+} -CAB mixtures at pH 8.50 by mole-ratio method¹³ indicated 1 : 2 M^{2+} -CAB complexes as the highest complexes formed in these systems. Therefore, the formation of hydroxo and 1 : 2 M^{2+} -CAB complexes with release of 2H^+ per M^{2+} would involved the following complexation equilibria,

The species, viz. LH^+ , L , M^{2+} , $M(OH)^+$, $M(OH)_2$, $M(H_{-1}L)^+$, $M(H_{-1}L)_2$, $M(H_{-1}L)(OH)$ were, therefore, considered to be present in the complexation equilibria. The $M(H_{-1}L)_2$ and $M(H_{-1}L)(OH)$ complexes being electroneutral were likely the ones precipitated at $pH \geq 8.5$.

Distribution of the complex species are shown in Figs. 3 and 4. M^{2+} ions were the major species upto pH 5. The complexes $M(H_{-1}L)^+$ and $M(OH)^+$ made their first appearance around pH 5.5 and passed through maximum [$M(H_{-1}L) \geq 50\%$, $M(OH)^+ \approx 12\%$] around pH 7.2. The complexes $M(H_{-1}L)_2$, $M(H_{-1}L)(OH)$ and $M(OH)_2$ were formed at still higher pH values. The major species at the start of precipitation ($pH \geq 9$) was $Co(H_{-1}L)(OH)$ in the case of Co^{2+} -CAB system, while in the Ni^{2+} -CAB system these could be both $Ni(H_{-1}L)(OH)$ and $Ni(OH)_2$.

Solution of the Co^{2+} complex assumed a red-purple colour (λ_{max} 575 nm with a shoulder at 520 nm) characteristic of an octahedral geometry, suggesting the possibility of apical coordination by side-chain Cl as in the copper complex (6). The Ni^{2+}

Fig 3 Species distribution curves of Co^{2+} -CAB system (1) LH^+ , F_L , L , F_M , Co^{2+} , (2) $Co(OH)^+$ (3) $Co(OH)_2$; (6) $Co(H_{-1}L)^+$ (8) $Co(H_{-1}L)_2$ (9) $Co(H_{-1}L)(OH)$

Fig 4 Species distribution curves of Ni^{2+} -CAB system (1) LH^+ , F_L , L , F_M , Ni^{2+} , (2) $Ni(OH)^+$ (3) $Ni(OH)_2$, (6) $Ni(H_{-1}L)^+$, (8) $Ni(H_{-1}L)_2$, (9) $Ni(H_{-1}L)(OH)$

complex solution assumed a yellow-brown colour (λ_{max} 480 nm) characteristic of a square-planar geometry¹⁴.

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